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Sustainable Energy Transition Pathways for Nepal : Towards Net Zero by 2045

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Energy system modelling, decarbonization, renewable energy transition, net-zero emissions, power sector optimization, climate policy, NDC targets, OSeMOSYS

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Executive Summary

This report explores sustainable energy transition pathways for Nepal in line with the national Net-Zero 2045 target. Nepal's energy system is currently dominated by hydropower, but heavy reliance on biomass for cooking and imported petroleum for transport and industry raises challenges for energy security, trade balance, and emissions reduction.

Using OSeMOSYS modelling, three scenarios were tested: a Business-as-Usual (BAU) case, a Reduction of Imports through Electrification of transport and industry (RIM), and a Carbon Neutrality and Negativity scenario (CNN) with electricity, hydrogen, and biomass with Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). Results show that electrification increases capacity and production, with hydropower leading in RIM and biomass with CCS playing a bigger role in CNN. Costs rise due to higher investment needs, but long-term stability is improved as dependency on imports decreases. Emissions are highest in BAU, moderately reduced in RIM, and fall most sharply in CNN due to emission caps and penalties after 2035.

Overall, the findings show that to achieve the 2045 net-zero target, deeper electrification and negative-emission technologies are essential.

1. Introduction:

Nepal is a small landlocked country with abundant freshwater sources. The main source of energy production is hydropower with a theoretical capacity of 83,000 MW and technical capacity of 42,000 MW [1]. Out of the capacity, a slight fraction has been used, with 3600 MW installed capacity in 2024. Hydropower dominates the energy production sector with a contribution of 99 percent [2] .

Almost the entire population has access to electricity. However, Nepal's wider energy system still depends a lot on traditional biomass, with nearly 87% of households using firewood for cooking and heating [3]. On top of that, the country relies on petroleum imports for transport and industry, which raises both energy security and trade balance issues. Strengthening energy sovereignty by maximizing the use of domestic renewable resources and expanding electrification in transport, cooking, and industrial sectors offers a pathway to reduce dependence on imported fossil fuels. Such a transition would not only lower import bills but also enhance national resilience, economic stability, and long-term self-reliance. To make an effective transition, modeling and optimization simulations are necessary to identify cost-effective strategies for generation, storage, and distribution, and to evaluate different scenarios for maximum impact with minimal risk.

Nepal has also announced a Net-Zero carbon emissions target by 2045 at the COP '26 Summit [4]. In order to reach this target, biomass and fuel wood, which are the major sources of energy, particularly in the residential sectors, diesel and gasoline in transportation and coal in the industrial sector need to be phased out.

2. Methodology:

The software used for the energy modelling was MUIO (Modelling User Interface for OSeMOSYS). OSeMOSYS is a linear optimisation energy system model designed to minimise total system costs while ensuring energy demands are met within specified constraints. For the input, data for 2022- 2024 were collected from various national sources, including the Water and Energy Commission Secretariat, Nepal Electricity Authority and IEA. The factors for the future projections, technology adoption rates, efficiencies, costs, and policy impacts will be assumed according to the trends shown internationally by reputed organisations.

Figure 1: Scenarios formed for optimization in OSeMOSYS

Three scenarios have been formed for the energy modelling as shown in Figure 1. The business-as-usual (BAU) scenario assumes that current energy consumption and emission trends will continue without major policy or technological interventions.

The Energy Sovereignty/ Reduced Imports (RIM) scenario deals with reducing imports through the electrification of the industrial and transportation sectors, which consume the petroleum derivatives imported into the country. This scenario was chosen to follow the electrification targets in Nepal's NDC 3.0 [5], while supporting a gradual reduction in energy imports. The electrification targets in the transportation sector for cars and buses were set as the annual lower limit, and petroleum imports were reduced to 50% compared to BAU by 2050.

The Carbon Neutrality and Negativity (CNN) scenario envisions a transition to a low- or negative-carbon energy system by phasing out petroleum-based fuels in transportation and industry, through the use of electricity and hydrogen based systems, integrating carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS), and deploying negative emissions technologies such as bioenergy with CCS, aiming not only to neutralise emissions but also to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere. This scenario was developed in line with Nepal's 2045 net-zero carbon emissions target announced at COP26.

The results from these scenarios will be used to analyse potential pathways for Nepal's energy system, assessing how different technology options, adoption rates, and policy measures could impact energy supply, demand, costs, and emissions. This provides a structured basis for evaluating sustainable and low-carbon energy strategies.

3. Results:

Electrifying the industry and transport sectors leads to a significant increase in system capacity, boosting total electricity production as can be seen in Figures 2 and 3. In the RIM scenario, Hydropower kept increasing until 2050, while the level of solar and wind remained constant after a certain point. However, in the case of the CNN scenario, hydropower grows more slowly, and there is instead a rise in the biomass with CCS, which has a negative emission rate.

Figure 2: Total installed capacity by energy source across different cases.

Figure 3: Total energy production by source (PJ) across different cases.

For the costs, in the RIM and CNN cases, for the increase in capacity, additional investment is needed in the sectors of hydropower and biomass with CCS respectively as shown by figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4 : Fixed costs of power generation by technology across different cases.

Figure 5 : Annualised investment costs of power generation technologies across different cases.

The costs of Electricity Imports dominate the variable costs in the Power Sector as shown by Figure 6. The variable costs of the various imports have decreased to 50% of the total imports in the BAU scenario. These changes are reflected proportionally across all types, since imports feed into multiple end-uses such as transport, industry, and residential demand.

Figure 6 : Variable import costs by fuel type across different cases

Figure 7 : Variable electricity import costs across different cases

Figure 8 : Total system costs across different cases (\$M USD)

Figure 8 shows that the most expensive out of all these scenarios is the CNN scenario. The difference between the CNN and BAU is \$1324.83 Million, and the difference between BAU and RIM is \$476.86 Million. This difference is about 3.1% and 1.1% of the GDP of Nepal in 2024.

Nepal doesn't have emissions in the power sector since a negligible amount of the electricity produced is through petroleum sources. A significant change was seen in industrial emissions after the reduction in imports. The usage of petroleum is slowly phasing out, leaving only coal in low-heat applications in 2050. The situation is similar in the CNN scenario. Here, the petroleum-based emissions are decreasing until a certain point. Figure 9 also shows the emergence of negative emission-based technology, which ultimately leads to the Carbon Neutrality Scenario by 2045, as shown by Figure 10.

Figure 9 : Transport CO₂ emissions by fuel across different cases.

Figure 10 : Industry CO₂ emissions by Heat across different cases.

Figure 11 : CO₂ emissions across different cases

For the total emissions, it is seen that the maximum emissions are seen in the BAU scenario. Using electricity in the transport and the industry sector seems to have contributed to lowering the emissions in the second scenario. The third scenario uses an emission cap and emission penalty from 2035, which made the slope decrease much faster than the other two cases.

5. Discussion:

The results show that capacity and electricity production rise when transport and industry are electrified. In the RIM case, most of the new capacity comes from hydropower, while solar and wind stop growing after a point. Solar and wind stagnation is linked to their higher relative costs than hydropower in the model inputs. This outcome suggests that without additional measures, the system remains heavily reliant on hydropower, limiting diversification and creating potential risks for long-term energy security and resilience. In the CNN case, hydropower grows more slowly, but biomass with CCS increases and brings negative emissions, which helps reach net-zero faster.

However, the biomass with CCS increases at an unprecedented rate. With the country not having a large biomass powerplant, the situation shown by this scenario is dubious which could be due to the cost data in the input not being reflected by the real-world scenario.

CNN achieves deeper decarbonisation, which comes at a higher cost; RIM balances the lower costs with moderate reductions.

On the cost side, shown in Figure 8, both RIM and CNN require higher upfront investment. However, the focus differs: RIM channels resources into expanding hydropower, while CNN directs them toward deploying biomass with CCS. Variable costs are primarily driven by electricity imports, highlighting that reducing imports not only lowers expenses but also strengthens system stability and energy independence. Regarding emissions, BAU locks the country into the highest trajectory, RIM achieves steady reductions through electrification, and CNN delivers the steepest decline after 2035 due to the introduction of caps and penalties, underscoring the trade-off between higher costs and faster decarbonization.

6. Policy Recommendations:

a. Electrification:

- Ensure 50% of new public buses and 30% of heavy-duty trucks are electric by 2030, with further scaling by 2035, supported by dedicated financing and institutional coordination.
- Target 100% electrification of industrial boilers and furnaces by 2045, supported by industrial heat pumps and solar thermal, alongside regulatory and investment support.

b. Long-term decarbonisation:

- Launch a 50–100 MW biomass with CCS pilot by 2035, scaling to 500 MW by 2045 enabled by policy incentives and financing mechanisms.
- Implement a carbon tax roadmap: \$10–15/ton by 2030, rising to \$50/ton by 2045, with revenues funding clean energy and social protection, and institutional strengthening.

7. Potential Areas for Future Research

Future studies could look more closely at seasonal changes, since variability in water availability directly affects hydropower reliability, making it critical to assess the role of storage and regional electricity trade in stabilising supply and reducing dependence on imports. Transport electrification can also be modeled in more detail, including freight, public transport, and charging needs, especially as Nepal plans to integrate a national railway system that could reshape energy demand. Hydrogen options for industry and transport could be explored alongside biomass with CCS, as both provide alternatives for hard-to-abate sectors and pathways to negative emissions. Finally, research into financing, investment policies, and real-world barriers is necessary to understand how such pathways can be translated from technical feasibility into practical implementation.

8. Conclusion

The modelling shows that Nepal is at a turning point. If the country continues on a BAU pathway, it will remain locked into high emissions, heavy fuel imports, and growing energy insecurity. However, shifting towards electrification of transport and industry, cutting imports, and investing in options like biomass with CCS can put Nepal on track for its 2045 Net-Zero target. For this to happen, policymakers must act quickly, scaling renewables and storage, implementing financing mechanisms, and building the governance and infrastructure to support the transition. A balanced mix of clean energy and negative-emission technologies will be essential for a sustainable, resilient, and self-reliant future.

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